

The Art of Interviewing

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ABSTRACT

The interview is a group of knowledge by a single person executing their own skills regarding of certain questions to be asked. It is an acknowledgement by a person to express their thoughts, ideas, and creativeness and so on. It is an Interview which collects the information by a middle man or agents because this interview helps to force someone to come out with the truth. Quantitative interview collects the message of customer satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

An interview is an intelligent question and answer dialogue between two or more persons for a purpose. And based on the purpose, the interview may be classified as personality interview, news interview, business interview, job interview, exit interview, exploratory interview, investigative interview, quantitative interview. the work of the newspaper reporter is, in a sense, one long interview, for he obtains the majority of his information by asking questions and noting the answers, but the published interview in which a writer gave word-for- word answer and described even the actions of the interviewee is no longer in fashion.

Personality interview

Personality interview is designed to focus on the intelligent, artistic and emotive life of a celebrity, whom people crave to know more about. If as an interview you try to proclaim your smartness to the

whole world, you will end up doing only that and note your job. A warm and sympathetic understanding of the interviewee will facilitate a good interview. An interview begins at moment you send in your card, or knock on the door; but the success or failure of it will depend entirely on the impression you make on your entrance. The responses obtained will be interesting, and for the junior who cares to observe them they hold important lessons. 'Now here is someone who isn't merely saying 'good morning' because it is customary. He means what he is saying; he obviously enjoys his 'good morning' and the fact that he is wishing me one is a compliment!'

News interview

News interview is meant to dig out news from a person often unwilling to parts. It could be a state top-secret, a department programmer being finalized, or something someone is trying to save embarrassment for oneself or others. What everyone would gladly talk about is not news but publicity. News, like gold, lies buried deep, mixed with sand and rock. Spotting it and refining it is the fine art of journalism.

Business and job interview

The business interview is the business of executives, probably over a five course feast accompanied by finish. The media person takes no business in such interview, except when they become major corporate news like mergers and takeovers. Job interview is

planned to select the right candidate for the right job, and an exit interview to make pleasant the unpleasant task of retrenchment of an employee or a group of employees.

Investigative interview

Investigative interview is normally conducted by investigative agencies like the CBI or the police corruption branch, with or without use of pain. An analytical journalist conducting an investigative interview has no power to force someone to come out with the accuracy. He has to coax or cajole, lay traps or outsmart.

Quantitative interview

Quantitative interview is conducted by market and opinion research administrations, and media take perception of it when it makes news, like popularity or pre-poll survey. Some media textbooks broadly divide interviews into qualitative and quantitative kind. Great interviews need two elements: preparation and strategy. Orient fallacy the Italian journalist and David frost the BBC interviewer have won international recognition for their monumental preparation and unerring instinct. When David frost interview john major, frost would know more about major's ancestry and rare ancestry and rare anecdotes about his father and mother than major him.

Recording the interview

Use a tape recorder. Memory is always unreliable and notes are always incomplete. People are usually willing to discuss their thoughts on public matters with the recorder going, especially if you have established their anonymity to begin with. Have your equipment ready and check it before you sit down with your interviewee. Have aspired tape ready to insert in case it will turn into a long interview, or a tape breaks.

Specialized interview

In the case of important individual interviews only a senior reporter is generally given the assignment well in advance. He spends a few days in studying the career of the great personality to be interviewed and frames the questions to which he wants an answer. The reporter is sometimes asked by the personality to submit the receipt of the interview report and if time permits, he should comply with the request and make the stipulation that when it is returned. If the interview

is to deal with a specific subject and is not intended to be a general survey of the world or of the locality in which the newspaper the reporter is published, the reporter must make certain that he has at least a rudimentary idea of the matters which he wishes his personality to talk about. It is no good being ushered into the great man's presence and then waiting for something to turn up.

Question and topics

The key to successful interviewing is to recognize that the kind of response you elicit depends on timing, the wording of your questions, and even your non-verbal messages. Whether you get long answers or short answer, firmly entrenched opinions or new ideas, ready-to-hand opinions or the background assumptions people don't usually think about will depend on how you ask the questions. Here are a number of variables that will determine the success of your interview:

Pace and style

The expectation that you want long answers can be conveyed explicitly but your non-verbal messages are even more important. Eye contact tells the interviewee that you are interested and should continue, as does waiting, expectantly, during a pause, rather than jumping in with another question.

Action listening

Social researchers make a distinction between fixed choice and open ended questions. For these interviews, you will be using mostly open ended questions. Treat them as such. Let the speaker say what he or she has to say before going on to the next question. Try to develop a feel for gauging when the informant has paused to gather his or her thoughts, and when the informant has pausing for the next question.

Structure

A more important distinction is between structured and semi-structured interviewing. In a structured interview, your interview schedule determines the wording and order of questions. The semi- interview is conducted more conversationally. You have about 20 questions that you will ask every interviewee, but draw them out by being an active listener.

Interviewing tips

- ❖ Start a pleasant conversation before you get down to the actual interview. People need a little transition time. Interviewees approach these sessions with four questions:
 1. What fix you want to know?
 2. Why fix you want to know?
 3. How much detail should I go into?
 4. Can I trust you with my reflections, moods?
- ❖ You are not important! Keep yourself, your opinions and capabilities, out of the discussion as much as thinkable once you get into the interview. There are several reasons for this. *Main*, this is your interviewee's moment in the spotlight, rare opportunity to speak without having to share time as one normally does in a conversation. *Second*, selectively reinforcing some of the interviewee's comments you might lead him to feel that it is safer to express certain opinions than others. *Third*, you may be making incorrect assumptions about the exact nature of the interviewee's beliefs.
- ❖ It's helpful to meet someplace where you will have privacy and would not be interrupted too often, but more important than that is meeting where the interviewee feels most comfortable.
- ❖ This is normal and is also why leisurely, semi-structure interviews, especially repeated ones, tend to give you more interesting result than shorter, structured interviews.
- ❖ When detailed to interview a personality, it is necessary to try and find out something about him before making any visit.

Conclusion:

As I concluded by saying that the task of an interview very offend, following a questionnaire pretend –this is stated in a general way, by thinking and communicating each other in more specific formulation so that it may be a realistic by interviewing. The interview is a method to judge the person between two each, by knowing their skills, speech and attitude of the person, by this I thank to my entire teacher, parents, friends by execution of effort and sincerity.

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